

C++ BASED ON CODE BLOCK IN CALCULATION OF BUILDING DESIGN

Shiva Fauziah¹, Andy Prasetyo, ST.,M.Kom²

D3 Informatics Engineering, Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic, Central Java

ABSTRACT

In the life of a building architect or designer, it is definitely in need of calculation from a designer to measure an object. And sketching or setting of several separate elements into a unified whole. With that, the design concept is an activity of translating the analysis result into a software package and then creating the system or improving the existing system.

Keyword : Code Block, C++, Building Design, Calculation

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Designing is a process for defining something that will be done using a variety of techniques and in it involves a description of the architecture and the details of the components and also the limitations that will be experienced in the process of the process.

According to Pressman (2009) the notion of development or building a system is the activity of creating a new system or replacing or improving the existing system as a whole.

so, it can be concluded that the design is drawing, planning, and making sketches or measurements of several separate elements into a whole and functioning unit. With this, the design definition is an activity to translate the results of analysis into software packages and then

create the system or improve the existing system.

1.2 Problem Formulation

How to design a design system formula in one programming by modifying an existing installation

1.3 Limitation of the problem

To avoid the expansion of the material, this problem is limited to covering the following things :

1. The discussion of the formula that will be given is only a simple technical formula from design of the build
2. This formula does not focus on the problems in terms of costs or anything else.

1.4 Objectives

1. the purpose of this journal is to complete the project assignments from the subjects of algorithms & programming

2. to help calculate problems from various problems from design

1.5 Benefit

The benefits of programming that I made to help people in design calculations

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Related studies

There are several studies related to the prediction of building space using various models/methods as analysis based on :

Francis D.K. ching “from,space and order” symbiotic relationship between the form of mass and space in architecture can be valued and found on several different scales.

Arnis rochma harani “the influence of building façade on the visual character of the area” indicators are arranged based on these variables then used as benchmarks in search for data and analyze.

Yosika mariana “building typology on pakubowono kebayoran baru, south jakarta” building façade is most often given an assessment by observers,architecture and lay community composition of a façade by considering all functional requirements in principle by creating

compositions proportional to structured vertical and horizontal elements material,color and decorative elements

2.2 Theoretical foundation

Design is a series of procedures to translate the results of analysis of a system into programming languages to describe in detail how the system components are implemented while waking up is an activity to create a new system or replace or improve existing systems in whole or in part.

Thus the design is an activity to translate the results of analysis into software packages and then create the system or improve the existing system. (Pressman 2009)

C ++ language is an object-oriented programming language to solve problems. CodeBlocks is a free, non-profit, open source and cross-platform integrated development environment program (Andy Prasetyo 2018)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The stages in this study are as follows:

- a. Data collection
- b. Grouping
- c. research testing
- d. Research evaluation

The method proposed in this study is CodeBlock Based C ++ Language Programming in a simple calculation from the design.

Following are the steps in this study:

1. Determine the calculation that will be calculated
2. Enter the numbers requested in the calculation

The following is the course flowchart of the program:

Figure 3.1 design flowchart

4. RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

The following is a simple technical calculation program from design of build design

```

1 #include <iostream>
2 #include <math.h>
3
4 using namespace std;
5
6 void persegi()
7 {
8     float s,l,k;
9
10    cout <<"==== MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING PERSEGI ===" <<endl;
11    cout <<"Masukan nilai sisi : ";cin>>s;
12    l=s*s;
13    k=4*s;
14    cout <<" luas persegi = " <<l<<endl;
15    cout <<" keliling persegi = " <<k<<endl;
16
17 }
18
19 void persegi_panjang()
20 {
21    float p,l,L,K;
22    cout <<"==== MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING PERSEGI PANJANG ===" <<endl<<endl;
23    cout <<" masukan panjang : ";cin>>p;
24    cout <<" masukan lebar : ";cin>>l;
25    L=p*l;
26    K=2*p+2*l;
27    cout <<" luas persegi panjang = " <<L<<endl;
28    cout <<" keliling persegi panjang = " <<K<<endl;
29 }
  
```

Figure 4.1 coding of the building space

```

30 void segitiga()
31 {
32     float A,a,t,L,K,miring;
33     cout <<"==== MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING SEGITIGA " <<endl<<endl;
34     cout <<" masukan alas = ";cin>>a;
35     cout <<" masukan tinggi = ";cin>>t;
36     L=0.5*a*t;
37     A=0.5*a; //sisi miring dari alas miring=sqrt(pow(A,2)+pow(t,2));
38     K=(miring*2)+a;
39     cout <<" luas segitiga = " <<L<<endl;
40     cout <<" keliling segitiga = " <<K<<endl;
41 }
42
43 void lingkaran()
44 {
45     float r,L,K;
46     cout <<"==== MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING LINGKARAN ===" <<endl<<endl;
47     cout <<" masukan jari-jari = ";cin>>r;
48     L=3.14*r*r;
49     K=3.14*2*r;
50     cout <<" luas lingkaran = " <<L<<endl;
51     cout <<" keliling lingkaran = " <<K<<endl;
52 }
  
```

Figure 4.2 coding of the building space

```

53 int main()
54 {
55
56     int pilih;
57     cout <<"==== PROGRAM MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING RUANG BANGUN ===" <<endl;
58     cout <<"MENU = " <<endl;
59     cout <<"1. persegi" <<endl;
60     cout <<"2. persegi panjang " <<endl;
61     cout <<"3. segitiga " <<endl;
62     cout <<"4. lingkaran " <<endl;
63     cout <<" masukan nomor bentuk bangunan = ";cin>>pilih;
64     cout <<endl;
65     if(pilih==1)
66     {
67         persegi();
68     } else if (pilih==2)
69     {
70         persegi_panjang();
71     } else if (pilih==3)
72     {
73         segitiga ();
74     } else if(pilih==4)
75     {
76         lingkaran();
77     } else
78     {
79         cout <<" masukan pilihan yang benar ";
80     }
81 } main();
  
```

Figure 4.3 coding of the building space

Explanation of code

#include <iostream> is used to display the function cout, cin and endl

#include <math.h> used to call the function sqrt and pow

Cout is used to output the program

Cin is used to enter the program

endl is used to enter one line to bringth mathematics

Pow is used for the rank function on the math

Main () used to hold the screen display

Following are the compiling result from a simple technical calculation program using codeblock by running the program and then entering the text according to what has been specified.

```

"E:\tugas sipa\nyoba ruang bngun\main.exe"
=== PROGRAM MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING RUANG BANGUN ===
MENU =
1. persegi
2. persegi_panjang
3. segitiga
4. lingkaran
masukan nomor bentuk bangunan =
  
```

Figure 4.4 Compiler result (from coding the building)

```

"E:\tugas sipa\nyoba ruang bngun\main.exe"
=== PROGRAM MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING RUANG BANGUN ===
MENU =
1. persegi
2. persegi_panjang
3. segitiga
4. lingkaran
masukan nomor bentuk bangunan = 3

=== MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING SEGITIGA

masukan alas = 5
masukan tinggi = 7
luas segitiga =17.5
keliling segitiga =5
=== PROGRAM MENGHITUNG LUAS DAN KELILING RUANG BANGUN ===
MENU =
1. persegi
2. persegi_panjang
3. segitiga
4. lingkaran
masukan nomor bentuk bangunan =
  
```

Figure 4.5 Compiler results and calculations

5.CLOSING

a. Conclusion

Based on the above research using C++ based on CodeBlock programming language for simple technical meetings from desugn engineering. This research is a take from many references that helped me in reviewing this journal task.

b. Suggestions

For more information about the formula another simple way to see more references to building thatn orders

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